

European long-term ecosystem, critical zone and socio-ecological systems research infrastructure
PLUS

Project web pages

Deliverable D6.2

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Author(s)

Iliyana Demirova, Pensoft Publishers
Slavena Peneva, Pensoft Publishers

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Preface

Dedicated project webpages need to be created and continuously updated for the eLTER PLUS project throughout the project duration and beyond, with the aim to create a designated eLTER PLUS section (a collection of eLTER PLUS pages with their own internal navigation) within the eLTER overall website. This deliverable explains the rationale behind the decision to create an eLTER PLUS website section rather than a separate website, lists the user groups and their interests, outlines the progress so far, explains the visual elements, and describes the planned actions related to improving the designated eLTER PLUS website section visually, content-wise and in terms of navigation and user friendliness.

Summary

A designated webpage was created for eLTER PLUS (<https://www.lter-europe.net/projects/elter-plus>) to outline the most important information about the project and provide an engaging landing page and point of reference for future project communication. Additionally, visual elements were developed to distinguish the eLTER PLUS pages from other parts of the website. The eLTER PLUS website section will be continuously updated and enriched with new pages and elements to create a multi-layered, user-friendly online resource where key information, promotional material and news and updates about the project can be easily accessed and browsed by visitors.

1. The eLTER PLUS webpages

1.1 Purpose, expected users and positioning

The eLTER PLUS webpages were created within the overall eLTER website (<https://www.lter-europe.net/>) with the purpose to provide a dedicated website section for information on the project, its outcomes, news and events, while at the same time highlighting that eLTER PLUS is a project belonging to a greater community and showcasing the relationships between the different eLTER elements and their relation to eLTER PLUS via interlinking. Further development of the site will continue as a coordinated activity led by the WP6 in eLTER PLUS. (More on the rationale behind placing eLTER webpages within the overall eLTER website structure available in section 1.3)

The eLTER PLUS website section will host a continuously updated collection of webpages designed with the purpose to showcase information on:

- The project and its objectives
- Media items produced by the project (press releases, brochures, videos, etc.)
- News and events specifically related to this project
- Key results coming from the project: policy briefs, factsheets etc.
- Dedicated project pages for the upcoming TA project calls and training events
- Gateway to internal project areas for project partners

The eLTER PLUS webpages are located in a dedicated section under the main menu item “Projects” on the homepage of the overall eLTER website. This structure highlights the relationship between the project, the eLTER RI and the international LTER-Europe network, while at the same time providing a logical and easy-to-access and find location to ensure every visitor can get there through a few clicks, see Fig 1.

Figure 1: Positioning of the eLTER PLUS webpages within the eLTER overall website.

In order to design the webpages as a functional part of the project, we defined its potential users and target groups, and specific information created for each group (only some examples listed) as follows:

Internal target groups:

- Project partners: e.g. information on project structure and Work packages, upcoming events, links to project material etc.
- Other members of the LTER-Europe community (site PIs, national coordinators, data managers etc.): e.g. information on project activities, advice how to become involved into the eLTER ESFRI process (links to eLTER PPP), news on pilots testing services, calls for joint activities etc.

External target groups:

- Scientific community: e.g., newsfeed and repository (links) of latest research published by eLTER PLUS partners; Case study pages; Public event announcements, etc.
- Peer Research infrastructures and projects: information on eLTER activities, calls for joint events, reports of staff training and pilot studies, etc.
- Ministries and other RI shareholders: news on development of project outcomes (e.g. novel services, engaging different user groups), updates on societal impacts, etc.
- Policy: e.g., policy related results such as policy briefs; news; videos in Media centre; events, etc;
- Access users: dedicated webpage for Transnational and Remote Access with details of the call and reports from visits, highlighting the key success stories, etc;
- General public: News, press releases, interviews of project PIs to highlight the links to society, etc.

1.2 Updating the eLTER overall website

There several aspects of the eLTER overall website that will be updated by the end of year one to accommodate the latest trends of in web design while also ensuring easy navigation and sustainability of the underlying software infrastructure. Current issues identified with the eLTER website:

- Uses old version of Plone - 4.3.19 (4321)
- Newest version of Plone not applicable on current servers as it only works with Python 3.0
- Uses a very archaic Plone theme from 2013 with limited possibility to visually edit website outlook
- Unclear navigation inherited from many years of adding new elements without thoroughly revising the structure
- Homepage not used in an optimal way to highlight the different elements of eLTER (network of site, RI, projects)

Based on these identified issues several steps will be applied to improve and modernise the website for users:

- Discuss several options for using a new underlying infrastructure based on the options for plugins, widgets and functionalities they offer and the user-friendliness of the underlying CMS (Considered: Plone, October, Wordpress, Wix)
- Choose a new theme with the following characteristics:
 - o Sliders are removed (considered archaic and studies show hardly anyone clicks through the different slides) and replaced by horizontal scrollable blocks of content (studies show that due to increased use of smartphones to view websites scrolling is becoming native to the majority of users)
 - o Use of large images in homepage to highlight the main elements of eLTER (Images are more appealing to users and encourage them to continue down the page. The text that is used is emphasized, clear and short.)
 - o Search Engine Optimisation (including plugins that ensure sharing content on social media is optimised – meaning that suggestion for a card including images and title is included for each page which then means that when someone posts a link a picture and selected text will always appear as multimedia with the post)
 - o Responsive design (the number of users using phones or tablets increasing on an annual basis)
- Improved navigation and recognisability of the overall website and within sections (for example for the PLUS section a homepage of the project itself will be created highlighting main elements such as overview, results, and library. The page will be also branded with the colour scheme described in section 2 here to provide visual cues that the user is now on the PLUS pages).

1.3 Current progress

An introductory informational page (Fig.2) was created and set up during the very first months of the project with the aim to provide a landing page and point of reference for all initial communication about the project (e.g. first newsletter, sent out in March 2020, social media activities, etc.). The webpage, available to view at <https://www.lter-europe.net/projects/PLUS> is nested within an area designated for the two back-to-back running projects, eLTER PPP and eLTER PLUS, in order to show their complementarity while highlighting the different aspects of the eLTER Research Infrastructure (RI) that they will support and enhance. Currently, the webpage contains information about:

- The project
- Key facts (such as duration, funding, leading institution etc.)
- Work programme (work packages)
- Timeline towards operation

LTER-Europe eLTER RI News Events **Projects** COVID-19 Statement Log in

eLTER Long-Term Ecosystem Research in Europe

OVERVIEW
of eLTER components

eLTER PLUS

CONTENTS

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- [2. eLTER PLUS Work Packages](#)
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In this section...

[elter ppp](#)

[elter plus](#)

eLTER Advanced Community Project (eLTER PLUS)

The project

The Advanced Community Project for the eLTER Research Infrastructure (eLTER PLUS) belongs to INFRAIA-01-2018-2019 programme of HORIZON 2020 and is built on three main pillars - networking, joint research activities and transnational, remote and virtual access. eLTER PLUS will conduct a performance test of the emerging eLTER RI while challenging, assessing and strengthening its operations. Selected sites and platforms in terrestrial, freshwater and coastal ecosystems will be used to study ecosystem integrity, impacts of climate change and endangered ecosystem services at a pan-European scale. Alongside these exemplary case studies eLTER PLUS will identify and assess innovative observational and analytical methods, elaborate detailed specifications of eLTER RI according to community needs (standard observations, site design), support community building and training, and pilot priority services (IT and other support).

Figure 2: eLTER PLUS project webpage

1.4 Rationale

The decision to nest the eLTER PLUS webpages within the overall eLTER website was taken for several reasons that rendered it more feasible than the creation of a standalone website:

- **More visible:** By placing it in the eLTER website, which is already popular and well visited, the chances to attract visitors and popularise the project and its news is higher.
- **Nested in context:** Being part of the overall project website will allow to highlight the connection between eLTER PLUS and the eLTER network, as well as the benefits the project will bring towards building the eLTER RI. Moreover, the project is placed together in the same website section with eLTER PPP (Fig. 3), which is running at the same time to highlight how the two projects will work together and separately to enhance different aspects of the eLTER RI.
- **Interlinked:** Being part of the overall eLTER website will allow to interlink content across the different eLTER projects and products in a more creative way. For example, a feature to link news to the project and visualise them on the project pages in an interactive way will be added together with the update of the overall project website. (See section 3)
- **Sustainable:** Being part of the eLTER overall website the existence and continuous updating of the eLTER PLUS webpages will be secured without risks of insufficient funding or changes in the webmaster.

The screenshot shows the top navigation bar of the eLTER website with links for LTER-Europe, eLTER RI, News, Events, Projects, and COVID-19 Statement. The main header features the eLTER logo and the text 'Long-Term Ecosystem Research in Europe'. Below the header, there is a search bar and a section titled 'Background'. The 'Background' section contains text about the integrated European Long-Term Ecosystem, critical zone and socio-ecological systems Research Infrastructure (eLTER RI) and mentions two major complementary Horizon2020 projects: eLTER PLUS and eLTER PPP. A sidebar on the left includes an 'OVERVIEW of eLTER components' button and a section titled 'In this section...' with links to 'elter ppp' and 'elter plus'.

Figure 3: A common explanation page navigates to the eLTER PLUS and PPP projects.

2 Visual elements

As part of the project branding development and in preparation for a redesign and modernisation of the overall eLTER website a new, slightly modernised version of the eLTER logo was created (Fig. 4), where gradient colours were exchanged for monochromatic colours to ensure the logo is more visible when used on promotional materials and in the future website. Additionally, a second line in the yellow – orange tones was added to the signature leaf to ensure that the socio-ecological elements are highlighted in the overall concept.

Figure 4: Comparison between the old eLTER logo (left) and the modernised version (right)

Following this redesign and with a vision to secure recognisability of the different products, while at the same time highlight their belonging to eLTER as a network a decision was taken that the logos for the two new projects (PPP and PLUS) and the eLTER RI will be built on the

basis of adding the acronym in a designated colour for each of them, that is also a colour belonging to the main eLTER colour scheme. (Fig. 5)

PPP RI PLUS

Figure 5: Colour coding of the main eLTER products for the purpose of visual recognition

As a result of this strategy a new logo (Fig. 5) was designed for eLTER PLUS to serve as a recognisable visual element and set the aesthetics of future eLTER PLUS visual materials, including colour-coding of new webpages, news labels, brochures, posters, infographs etc.

Figure 5: eLTER PLUS project logo

Signature colour:

 #40907A (Hex); 64 : 144 : 122 (RGB)

This particular colour was selected to designate the project based on its relation to the already existing colours in the eLTER logo and to respect colour coding already existing in the internal project communication, thus creating continuity both with the external and internal visual designator accepted by the community.

3 Future development

3.1 Development process

Step 1: An overall redesign of the general eLTER website is scheduled by the end of year one of this project (details in section 1.2), where the whole website will be redesigned to follow the latest trends in web design and to enhance user-friendliness. The new infrastructure on which the project will be built will also allow for more functionalities and widget to be installed to ensure truly interactive content. This work will be planned together with the eLTER PLUS project communications team and coordination, and led by WP6 lead (Pensoft).

Step 2: The eLTER PLUS website section will be upgraded not only visually to better reflect the selected colour coding but also in terms of functionalities. The following elements will be added to enhance content and provide places where important products and elements will be stored:

- Media centre (to host brochures, posters, videos and press releases, policy briefs, other public outreach)
- Library (to host publications and public deliverables coming from the project)
- News section
- Events section

Any other pages that are necessary will be added as the project develops (e.g. dedicated resource to highlight policy briefs coming from the project).

Step 3: The eLTER web pages will be continuously updated throughout the project duration and beyond. Being part of the overall eLTER website their sustainability is secured regardless of changes in web master or the end of project funding.

3.2 Evaluation of use and frequency of updates

To evaluate the success of the eLTER PLUS webpages, Google analytics is installed that will provide both qualitative and quantitative indicators regarding the usage of these web resources.

Quantitative: Number of users and visits will be monitored (min 2000 per year)

Qualitative: Page depth (min 3 pages per session) will give an insight on the general interest of visitors; Geographical distribution will be used to evaluate outreach and international relevance; since collecting personal data of users is not GDPR compliant Google analytics data will be fully anonymized. However, key individual pages such as library (for scientists) and policy briefs (for policy-makers) will be monitored separately as indicators to what extent the website is visited by the respective user group.

The following plan outlines the baseline activities and frequencies from M3 onwards:

1. Flyer – each year the project will develop an updated version of the project flyer
2. Press releases – roughly one press release per year (this number is a subject to change in accordance with the necessities of the project)
4. Electronic newsletter – one newsletter every quarter
5. News and Events on the website – minimum one update per month
6. Social networks activity – minimum one post per week

4. Conclusions

Deliverable 6.2 describes the process for creation of clear project identity and webpages. To maintain a consistent project identity and keep the relevant target groups well informed, the communication and dissemination team will update the project website on a regular basis, and create promotional materials with the most recent project updates. The web information will be streamlined with the overall progress of the eLTER ESFRI process and linked to the eLTER PPP web activities.